

IMPORTANCE OF DEVELOPMENT OF PISTACHIO FARMING IN UZBEKISTAN

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It is no secret that water reserves are limited in the territory of our republic. The way to solve existing problems is to organize efficient use, develop methods of efficient use of existing water resources, selective cultivation of drought-resistant, low-water consumption and high-yield plant species is one of the problems in the field of forestry. In our opinion, one of the plant species that can meet the above requirements is the pistachio tree (*Pistacia vera* L.).

As we mentioned above, we have 7.8 million hectares of dry land suitable for pistachio plantations in our country. Of these, 3 million hectares at altitudes of 650-1200 meters above sea level are considered the most suitable areas. Today, the existing pistachio groves cover an area of less than 100,000 hectares. The rest of the land is currently used as dryland crops and pastures with low profitability. If these areas are converted into pistachio plantations, employment will be provided to the local population living in these areas, very large unproductive areas will become a good source of income, food and energy sources (firewood) will be provided to the population, land degradation will be prevented, land reclamation will be improved, and wildlife will increase. the creation of a favorable environment will lead to a change in climate conditions and, finally, to an increase in the export potential of our country.

We can develop pistachio farming in our country in three directions:

The first direction is the establishment of intensive pistachio gardens. In this direction, pistachio growing has been widely supported by the developed countries - Iran, USA, Turkey, Southern European countries and China. In this direction, high agrotechnical measures (introduction of irrigation, mineral or organic fertilization, use of biostimulants and growth substances and hokoza) are carried out in pistachio plantations, and high yields were obtained.

The second direction is an extensive method, which has been used in our Republic until now. In this method, wild pistachio seeds or sprouts are planted in a permanent place, almost no agrotechnical treatments are given, and the yield is very low.

The third direction is the simultaneous use of the previous two methods, planting seeds or seedlings of pistachio trees in a permanent place and welding works and agrotechnical measures are carried out in this place. Agrotechnical processing procedure: partial shaping of trees, loosening of seedlings, fertilizing and, when necessary, fighting against diseases and insects are carried out.

All directions have advantages and disadvantages, so the choice of which direction is made based on the conditions of the place where pistachio plantations are established. It is advisable to use the first direction in areas with a dense population and a level of water supply, the second direction in mountainous areas with a small local population, and the third direction in low-population but plain areas. The higher prices of wild pistachios compared to cultivated pistachios (wild pistachios are known as "organic") in global markets indicate that extensive pistachio plantations can also be profitable.

In recent years, cultivation of cultivated pistachios on large areas of our country has been planned and is now being planted on many areas. In particular, the construction of pistachio groves for 10,000 hectares in Nurota State Forestry, 2,5,000 in Dehkhanabad State Forestry, 2,5,000 in Qamashi State Forestry and 5,000 in Andijan State Forestry is underway. In addition to these forest farms, many new pistachio groves are being established by farmers and residents in a number of other forest farms. But at the same time, there are a number of factors that limit the reproduction of these pistachios, which are as follows:

The pistachio tree comes into harvest late (usually at the age of 6-8). Because of this, people are not interested in planting this pistachio tree.

1. The population living in lands suitable for pistachios are mainly engaged in animal husbandry. Therefore, there is an opinion among them that the increase of pistachios leads to the decrease of pastures.

2. Lack of knowledge about pistachio organization and maintenance activities.

3. Lack of necessary specialists.

At the same time, there are ways to solve these problems, and nowadays, there is a large-scale promotion of pistachio farming, spreading knowledge about pistachio farming to the general public. Generally, when newly planted pistachios are well protected, pastures recover very quickly, with an increase in grasses that

are good for livestock and less grasses that are not. In protected pistachio pastures, the grass grows very quickly and productivity increases by 5-10 times compared to unprotected pastures. For example, in 2018, the height of the grass reached 1.5 meters in the protected young pistachio plantations in the Khanabad forest department of the Andijan State Forestry, and it did not exceed 10 cm in the unprotected pasture areas.

Another way to develop pistachio farming in our republic and increase its productivity is grafting pistachio buds on wild pistachio trees. Scientists of the Research Institute of Forestry have isolated 20 varieties and forms of the pistachio tree with large fruits, open-mouthed and fertile. The work of organizing mother plantations and collections of these varieties and forms in different regions of our Republic has been started. For example, there is a mother plantation and collection in the Gallaorol section of the Jizzakh State Forestry. Similarly, work on the organization of collection and mother plantations was started in Saksonota forest department of Tashkent region, Khanabad forest department of Andijan region, Bobotog forest farms in Surkhandarya. In 2019-2020, it is planned to establish collection and nursery plantations in Nurota State Forestry of Navoi Region, Fozilman Forest Department of Samarkand Region, and Qamashi State Forestry in Qao'qadarya.

One of the ways to reduce the cost of pistachio plantations and to recover costs faster is to use row spacing. It is possible to grow non-traditional plants as well as traditional dry crops (peas, mashar and khokozo). For example, it is possible to organize sorghum, anzur onion, fodder grass, honey plants, and firewood plantations.

Only local seeds and seedlings should be used in pistachio orchards. Recently, it is often heard that it is necessary to bring pistachio seeds and seedlings from Iran, Turkey and other countries and plant them. But during the past period, a number of diseases and pests entered our country from seeds and seedlings brought from foreign countries, which had a negative effect on plants. Even after the best quarantine inspection, seeds and seedlings are still susceptible to disease and insect transmission.

Land suitable for pistachios in our republic is one of our untapped resources.

CONCLUSION

In the future, Uzbekistan has the opportunity to become the world leader in pistachio cultivation and export. Taking these reasons into account, we think it is appropriate to grow our own pistachio varieties and forms without importing

pistachio seeds and seedlings from abroad. It would be good if forestry experts were involved and their control was introduced.

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